

Quantum Excited States and the Hypergeometric Differential Equation

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Recently, there has been interest in formulating the bound state Schrodinger and Klein-Gordon equations, (with certain potentials) as a hypergeometric differential equation from which Rodrigues polynomial solutions follow. In (1), a generalized hypergeometric equation is brought into standard hypergeometric form $p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} y + q(x) \frac{d}{dx} y + \lambda y = 0$ ((1)) where λ is the eigenvalue, $p(x)$ at most a quadratic polynomial and $q(x)$ at most a linear one. ((1) focuses on the Hulthen potential.)

In early notes, it was shown one may write the solution of a bound state as $W(x) = W_0(x) D_n(x)$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction, and obtain for $D_n(x)$ in the nonrelativistic case:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} D_n(x) - \frac{1}{m} \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right] D_n(x) = \lambda D_n(x) \quad ((2))$$

For the relativistic Klein-Gordon case, a similar equation holds (there is no $-1/2m$, $-1/m$ is replaced with -2) and λ is related to $E^2 - m_0^2$. Equation ((1)) is very similar to the hypergeometric form if the spatial ground state flux $[d/dx W_0/W_0]$ is a linear polynomial. The solution of the harmonic oscillator follows immediately from this case.

In this note, we examine the relativistic form of ((2)) from the Klein Gordon equation together with transformations $z=f(x)$ such that ((1)) is still satisfied. This places constraints on $[d/dx W_0/W_0]$, the ground state spatial flux, which we believe is a physical quantity. We then try to find a scalar potential in the Klein Gordon equation which is compatible with the constraint on $[d/dx W_0/W_0]$. Different transformations $z=f(x)$ lead to different possible potentials.

The approach used here seems to be different from that of (1).

Approach of (1)

In (1), bound states of the Hulthen scalar potential $-z/[1-qz]$ where $z = S_0 \exp(-ax)$ ((3)), used in the Klein-Gordon equation, are found using the idea of a hypergeometric differential equation and Rodrigues polynomials. The starting point is to consider a generalized hypergeometric equation:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + \frac{d}{dx} W \left[\frac{t(x)}{s(x)} \right] + \frac{d(x)}{[s(x)^2] W} = 0 \quad ((4))$$

Here $t(x)$ is at most a linear polynomial and $s(x)$ and $d(x)$ are at most quadratic.

Given the Klein-Gordon equation in one dimension with a particular potential, one may determine if it may be written in the form of ((4)). In particular, for the Hulthen potential ((3)), one first performs a transformation $z = \exp(-ax)$ and rewrites the Klein-Gordon bound state equation in terms of z . One then notes that this equation matches ((4)) with x replaced with z . Given that it does, it is a candidate for a Rodrigues polynomial solution i.e. the Nikiforov-Uvarov approach may be used (1).

In particular, it is argued in (1), that if an equation may be written as ((4)), it may be transformed using $W(x)=P(x) y(x)$ into:

$$s(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} y + g(x) \frac{dy}{dx} + \lambda y(x) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

such that $y(x)$ is given by Rodrigues formula. Full details are given in (1) and are not considered here.

Ground State and Interaction Equation

In a previous note (2), it was argued the Schrodinger equation for bound states may be written as two equations. First, $W(x)$ is written as $W_0(x) D_n(x)$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction. $W_0(x)$ satisfies the Schrodinger equation and a second equation ((2)) applies to $D_n(x)$. For the relativistic Klein-Gordon bound state equation one has for the interaction equation, a very similar equation as the nonrelativistic one:

$$- \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} D_n(x) - 2 \left[\frac{d}{dx} W_0 / W_0 \right] \frac{d}{dx} D_n(x) = \text{constant} D_n(x) \quad ((6))$$

The constant satisfies: $E^*E = E_0^*E_0 + \text{constant}$ where E_0 is the ground state energy.

We take ((6)) as our starting equation and unlike (1) insist $W(x)=W_0(x) D_n(x)$ and not $R(x) D_n(x)$ where $R(x)$ is a polynomial of order one (1). In order for ((6)) to be a hypergeometric equation, constraints must be imposed on $[d/dx W_0 / W_0]$. We call $[d/dx W_0 / W_0] = b(x)$ to simplify the writing. The Klein-Gordon equation with a scalar potential:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0(x) + [m_0 + V(x)]^2 W_0(x) = E^*E W_0(x) \quad ((7))$$

Is then satisfied by $W_0(x)$, the ground state wavefunction.

The first term in ((7)) may, however, be written in terms of the spatial flux $b(x)$ i.e.:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{d}{dx} W_0 / W_0 \right] = (1/W_0) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0 - \left[\frac{d}{dx} W_0 / W_0 \right]^2 \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Or } \frac{d}{dx} b(x) = 1/W_0 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0 - b(x)^2 \quad ((9))$$

Thus ((7)) becomes:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} b(x) - b(x)b(x) = [E^*E - m_0^2] - V(x)^2 - 2m_0V(x) \quad ((10))$$

Thus, if $b(x)$ has a constrained form (to fit the hypergeometric equation), this must have a consequence on $V(x)$.

Transformations

Equation ((6)) is already in the form of hypergeometric equation if $b(x)$ is of a certain form (i.e. is a linear polynomial). The full hypergeometric equation ((1)), however, is of the form (3):

$$p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} y(x) + q(x) \frac{d}{dx} y(x) + \lambda y(x) = 0 \quad ((1)) \text{ or } ((11))$$

Where $p(x)$ is at most quadratic and $q(x)$ at most linear in x . Thus, given that ((6)) has $P(x)=1$, one may consider transformations $z=f(x)$ which bring in at most a quadratic polynomial in z in front of $d/dz d/dz y(z)$ and a linear polynomial in front of $d/dz y(z)$. $\lambda y(z)$ is unchanged.

We first consider the transformation $z=\exp(-ax)$ like in (1), to see what potential $V(x)$ is obtained. In such a case: $d/dx y(x) = -az d/dz y(z)$ so ((6)) becomes:

$$a^2 z^2 \frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} y - az [b(z)] \frac{dy}{dz} - a \frac{dy}{dz} + \lambda y(z) = 0 \quad ((12))$$

z^2 in the first term on the LHS is already a quadratic. Let us set $a=1$ to simplify. Thus:

$-z [b(z)] + 1$ must be a linear polynomial.

A first guess might be to set $b(x)=\text{constant}$. This is equivalent to:

$$b(z) = b(x) = \frac{d}{dx} W_0(x) / W_0(x) = \text{constant} \text{ or } W_0(x) = \exp(-\text{constant } x)$$

This is not a very interesting solution. Another choice is:

$$b(z) = [P + Qz]/z \quad \text{or} \quad b(z) = P/z + Q$$

Then:

$$-Z \frac{d}{dz} b - b^2 b = (E^2 E - m_0^2 m_0) - V^2 V - 2mV$$

Let $e = E^2 E - m_0^2 m_0$

$$P/z + P^2 P/z^2 - Q^2 Q + 2PQ/z = e - V^2 V - 2mV \quad ((13))$$

Try $V = A + B/z$ as a solution. Then, the RHS of ((13)) becomes:

$$e - A(A+2m) - B^2 B/z^2 - AB/z - B(A+2m)/z$$

Equating powers of z gives:

$$Q^2 Q - e = A(A-2m) \quad \text{This gives } A(Q)$$

$$P^*P = B^*B \quad \text{Let } P=B$$

$$P(1-2Q) = -2AB - 2m = -2AP - 2m$$

$P(1-2Q) = -2A(Q)P - 2m$ This can be solved for P in terms of Q which should yield a solution. Thus, it seems:

$V(z)=A+B/z$ is a possible potential. In terms of x, $V(x)= A+B\exp(-x)$ which may be a potential of interest according to (1).

Another possible transformation is:

$$dz/dx = z + d \quad \text{or } z=(-1/a) \exp(-ax) + dx \quad (\text{We set } a=1.)$$

Then ((6)) becomes:

$$(z+d)^*(z+d) d/dz d/dz y + (z+d) (b) dy/dz + dy/dz + \lambda y = 0$$

$$\text{One may try } b = [P+Qz]/(z+d) \quad \text{or } b = [P + Qz] / (z+d)$$

The LHS of ((6)) becomes:

$$-1 [Q - Qz / (z+d) + [P^*P + Q^*Qz^*z + 2PQz] / (z+d)^*(z+d)]$$

$$\text{For the potential, one may try } V(z)=[Az+B]/(z+d)$$

Plugging into ((6)) and evaluating powers of z one has:

$$z^0 \quad Q + P^*P/d^*d = e + B^*B/d - 2mB/d \quad \text{This gives } P(B)$$

$$Z^4: -[Q(z+d)^2 + Qz(z+d) + P^*P + Q^*Qz^*z + 2PQz] = e(z+d)(z+d) - A^*Az^*z - B^*B - 2BAz - 2m(Az+B)(z+d)$$

$$Z^2: -[Q+Q+Q^*Q] = e - A^*A - 2mA \quad \text{This yields } A(Q)$$

$$Z: -Q^2d - Q - 2PQ = e^2d - 2BA - 2m(AB)$$

With Q set to a number, A(Q) is a number and one may solve the last equation z: for B. It seems it is a quadratic equation which should have a solution if parameters are adjusted suitably.

Thus: $V(z) = [Az+B] / (z+d)$ seems to be a possible potential. In terms of x , one has:

$V(x) = [A \exp(-x) + B] / (\exp(-x) + d)$ which looks similar (although not exactly the same as) the Hulthen potential.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that for either the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equation (bound states), one may write $W(x) = W_0(x)D_n(x)$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction. This leads to $W_0(x)$ satisfying the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equation and a hypergeometric equation for $D_n(x)$ if $b(x) = [d/dx W_0 / W_0]$ is constrained so the factor in front of $d/dx D_n(x)$ is a linear polynomial. This constrained $b(x)$ may be used in the Klein-Gordon or Schrodinger equation with the quadratic $d/dx d/dx W_0(x)$ term replaced using $d/dx b(x) + b^2 = [d/dx d/dx W_0] / W_0$ to find a compatible potential. An additional procedure may also be used. The hypergeometric equation allows for a quadratic polynomial in front of $d/dx d/dx D_n(x)$. The interaction equation ((2)), however, has a constant 1. Thus, one may consider transformations $z=f(x)$ which bring a quadratic polynomial in front of $d/dz d/dz D_n(z)$ and a linear in front of dy/dz . In such a case, $dz/dx (b) d/dz D_n(z)$ must be such that $dz/dx (b+1)$ is a linear polynomial. This places constraints on the form of $b(z)$. $b(z)$ may be entered into the Klein-Gordon (or Schrodinger equation) and a compatible potential found.

References

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